

New Era of Accounting System based on Artificial Intelligence (AI)- Triadic-Entry Accounting

Chinmoy Ghosh

Lecturer of Commerce, East Calcutta Girls' College, Kolkata India

ABSTRACT: Triadic- Entry Accounting is not the term for it, there are considerable benefits in writing deals to an Artificial Intelligence (AI). Important like journal entries are presently recorded in an association's subledgers (e.g., Accounts Receivable) and general tally, recording deals on an Artificial Intelligence (AI) would give visibility into affiliated deals.

KEY WORDS-Artificial Intelligence (AI), Triadic- Entry Accounting

INTRODUCTION

Triadic- entry accounting is a scholarly conception conceived by the late Yuji Ijiri, a professor at Carnegie Mellon University. It presents a frame for a new way to do accounting, replacing the standard account formula (Means = Arrears Equity) with a more complex frame.

Basically, what Yuji has done is taken the familiar conception that the change in Wealth is equal to Income (effectively the same as the standard account formula) and added on some new generalities to give further information about where the association is headed. The idea is that account could be unnaturally tied to soothsaying and, thus, enable better strategic decision timber.

Whether or not it's worth pursuing this indispensable account system is over for debate, but it clearly is not presently being used in any significant way. In that paper we try to establish, indeed if controllers and companies could get over the monumental chain of moving down from double- entry account, it's impracticable to use a more complex system. It's hard enough to get the account right when there are only two sides of an entry.

Accounting is one of the most important, yet daunting and precious departments in nearly all companies. Accountants oversee all fiscal operations of a business to help it run easily and efficiently. These include preparing and assaying fiscal statements (e.g., cash inflow, income statement, balance distance), paying levies on time, and maintaining the companies' general tally (GL). All these tasks bear a great deal of mortal commerce that takes time and plutocrat; no matter how careful an hand may be, there's always the chance for mortal error, which could balloon and lead to ruinous fiscal results in the future.

While triadic- entry account is not the term for it, there are considerable benefits in writing deals to a Artificial Intelligence (AI). Important like journal entries are presently

recorded in an association's subledgers (e.g., Accounts Receivable) and general tally, recording deals on a Artificial Intelligence (AI) would give visibility into affiliated deals.

As artificial intelligence has done for every assiduity, it's making a significant impact in the world of accounting and finance. From saving time and plutocrat and furnishing perceptivity, AI- enabled systems for account and finance are the way finance professionals and their enterprises will stay competitive and attract the coming generation as workers and guests.

Recent trends have made artificial intelligence (AI) available in accounting software, which is making a significant impact on the account and finance sector, just like it has for every other assiduity. With the help of AI, counting tasks that formerly took hours and days to negotiate can now be completed more directly in just a bit of the time

For case, an Artificial Intelligence (AI) could be created once a contract is inked, also a purchase order could be issued against that contract, bills against that purchase order, payments against those bills, etc., tracking any issues that arise along the way. There would be a unique ID related to the contract/ purchase order/ bills in that chain to tie all of those separate pieces together.

Having a tally that fluently shows the entire string of affiliated deals would not only give excellent inspection records, it would allow both parties to a sale to have real- time status updates. Every time the Artificial Intelligence (AI) is streamlined with a new record, both parties to the sale are suitable to incontinently see the update. Plus, with Artificial Intelligence (AI). Technologies similar as Ethereum, you're suitable to circumscribe access to the parties to the sale. I look forward to seeing what's coming as this technology evolves and reaches wide relinquishment. It's just getting started.

Secretary or accountants has its roots in ancient societies, some as old as 5000 times ago and thus, we've substantiation of Single- Entry Account indeed during the Mesopotamian period.

Objective of the study - How Triadic- entry accounting system work in the current era of accounting

PROCEDURE OF ACCOUNTING WITH NEW COMPOSITION OF TRIADIC- ENTRY ACCOUNTING SYSTEM

Single- Entry Accounting

, on the one hand, was a simple, easy to maintain the system as it was a one-sided account system but on the other, it was insolvable to authenticate or examine its responsibility. Therefore, with time, the man realized that the procedure of account demanded further translucency and responsibility and should be suitable to answer questions like

- Who paid what?
- Who owes how important?
- Which debts are overdue?
- Why is plutocrat missing?
- Where did we lose plutocrat?
- Which deal gave the stylish profit?

Dawn of Double- Entry Accounting system

“Difficulty, effectiveness, and originality are considered to be the three constituents of intellectual beauty. Double- entry secretary is plant to have all three,”-Yuri Ihri

. The downsides of Single- Entry Account came the detector point to look for a further comprehensive structure and therefore, came into being the Double- Entry Account.

This new form was developed nearly 600 times ago with the purpose of making the account system more comprehensive and hence, rather of maintaining one tally, the accountant keeps two; one for incoming and the other for gregarious.

Describing this transition, the account practitioner Yuji Ijiri explains, “First there was single entry secretary — just writing down what happened. Also came a double- entry — what happened has to be explained by logic by another account.”

Although the Double- Entry Account system of secretary was much more advanced and effective than Single- Entry Accounting, still there were several excrescencies in this too. As there was no connection between the different sets of Books, the records were separate and thus, demanded in translucency and were delicate to corroborate. This led to a great trust deficiency between the colourful stakeholders, like investors, lenders and/ or the state.

The debut of Triadic- entry Accounting system

“Ubi non est ordo, ibi est confusio!”

. (Where there's no order, there's confusion)-Luca Pacioli

. The defects and excrescencies of the Double- Entry Account led to the need of an frugality-wide account system, one that would help in doing down with huge quantities of administration and pave the way for a foolproof and reliable account system.

Therefore, Triadic- Entry Accounting is a step ahead of the traditional Double- Entry Account; one that will relieve the clerks and companies from tedious troubleshooting and help remove the distrust, frauds or manipulations faced by them.

How Does Triadic- Entry Accounting Work?

“It's tough to lie when everybody is watching.”-Ian Grigg

An outstanding conception conceived by the late Yuji Ijiri, a professor at Carnegie Mellon University, Triple-Entry Accounting presents a frame for a new and complex way to do account. The conception has come into focus in recent times when Ian Grigg who associated it with Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology and vulgarized it as he believed that account should no longer be fully private.

It's veritably essential to understand what's a Artificial Intelligence (AI) and how does it work? In simple terms, Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to a digital tally that's distributed among multiple locales in order to insure security and ease of access encyclopaedically. At present, this technology is primarily used for bitcoin and other crypto currencies and has just entered the account processes but sphere experts comment that it's only a matter of time till it'll entirely disrupt the account processes.

The term Triadic- Entry Account is kindly deceiving as there is not any third entry; rather, a third element is added to the disbenefit and credit system. The common thread or the list element is Artificial Intelligence (AI) that links the books together and helps in linking two separate double entries and can potentially be viewed for external auditing purposes.

So, rather of individual enterprises having their own books for the sale, they go through a contract which putatively includes every aspect of a sale; what the product was, who's the dealer, who's the buyer, etc. and over all, it's digitally inked.

In the Triadic- entry Accounting system, all counting entries are cryptographically sealed by a third entry and therefore, it works as a interference towards manipulations and fiscal fraud. In traditional Double- Entry Account a company's tally can be compromised by any of the weak mortal links, may be a hand or a chronicler or indeed an adjudicator. But this unique system of Triple-Entry Accounting leaves no space for any loose, weak mortal link as it's inflexible.

As Artificial Intelligence (AI) are fully automated and decentralized, once an entry is recorded, it cannot be edited, altered or removed. The loftiest position of encryption technology ensures the delicacy of each sale, digitally inked, leaving no gaps for crimes and at the same time empirical by all.

The deals recorded on the Artificial Intelligence (AI) using triadic entry simplifies the entire double- entry account process as formerly a sale is recorded on the Artificial Intelligence (AI) system by one of the two accountants, the other party can also view the particular double entry, fluently review it, and have it recorded automatically in its own books.

Therefore, Triadic- Entry Accounting is set to potentially revise the future of secretary as Artificial Intelligence (AI)

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account will literally halve the double- entry deals recorded. This will help the clerks greatly by saving their time and furnishing them the occasion to concentrate more on value-added places within the profession.

Let’s examine what it does

- ❖ It takes the reliance out from the Adjudicators to insure thickness.
- ❖ It introduces a public tally where all sharing realities mandatorily host all counting entries.
- ❖ It thereby establishes a tone- regulated and participated terrain amongst all stakeholders.
- ❖ It therefore, ensures that the larger purpose of secretary and auditing does n’t suffer because of crimes or deletions, immaterial of whether caused designedly or unintentionally.
- ❖ Being tamper- evidence, it brings around trust into the books.
- ❖ Triadic- Entry Account allows coordinating the balance, the sale, and the reporting process.
- ❖ By keeping anon-biased record, Triple-Entry Accounting reduces the probabilities of crimes, frauds or manipulations.
- ❖ With this system of account, there's a perfect inspection trail as it creates an inflexible history of all the exchanges within the system.

Future of Triadic- entry Accounting system

“Last but not least, with triadic entry account, for the veritably first time, we will seamlessly follow the world’s plutocrat.”- David Hartley

CONCEPT OF YUJI IJIRI

Diagram-1

Triadic- Entry Accounting is a logical result to keep the mistrust and dubitation at bay and to recapture the trust and faith of stakeholders in companies. There are relatively a many realities that are espousing Triple-Entry Accounting but at the moment aren't suitable to reach the optimum performance position because tone-auditing checks need numerous actors. Explaining this abecedarian factor David Hartley says, “It’s the same problem as the first telephone. It only is sensible if there are enough others.”

David Hartley bets on the utility of the system and points out that, “Especially transnational companies will save a lot of time and plutocrat when creating inspection documents. The inspection itself is also accelerated.”

Therefore, the Triadic- Entry Accounting really has considerable benefits and as a tally that shows up the whole string of deals, whether bills generated or paid,etc. it would prove to be an excellent inspection record. A real- time status update is another major benefit at the same time availability from anywhere at any time is a important- demanded convenience.

Moment the companies may not be prepared for this dislocation but gradationally this unique technology will evolve and shall substantiation wide relinquishment, this is just the morning of a new period in accounting!

MODELS AND METHODS

Correlation of concept of Yuji Ijiri and the concept widely known as Artificial Intelligence (AI) (block chain) method with the help of input- affair (IPO) model

Ijiri try to established in his research paper (1986) ,the above concept as above

Now a days the according to the fast procedure of accounting system,for ensuring efficiency and effectiveness of accounting system which relates to

- Accuracy
- Transparency
- Easy detection of errors

- Easy detection of frauds
- Easiest procedures of reconciliation

One dimension is added with so called double entry system that is the monumental pillar of Triadic- Entry Accounting system, that is Artificial intelligence (AI), every reciprocal debit and simultaneously credit entry verified and authenticated by AI.

NEW CONCEPT IS AS FOLLOWS

Diagram-2

According to the Diagram-2, this concept widely known as artificial intelligence (AI) (Block chain) method. That will follow the rule of wisdom {Input- Affair (IPO) Model}

The Input- Affair (IPO) Model is a functional graph that identifies the inputs, labours, and needed processing tasks needed to transfigure inputs into labours. The model is

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occasionally configured to include any storehouse that might be in the process as well. The inputs represent the inflow of data and accoutrements into the process from the outside. The

processing step includes all tasks needed to prompt a metamorphosis of the inputs. The labours are the data and accoutrements flowing out of the metamorphosis process.

Diagram-3

So, we can say that according to Diagram-3 the concept of **yuji ijiri** is now a days in the current era is established by (AI)/ (Block chain) method by follow up the Input- Affair (IPO) Model.

CONCLUSION

We conclude that Accounting is one of the most important, yet daunting and precious departments in nearly all companies. The concept of **yuji ijiri** is now a days in the current era is established by (AI)/ (Block chain) method by follow up the Input- Affair (IPO) Model.

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